

Protocol for semi-structured interviews: Policy actors (i.e. both policymakers and wider policyworkers)

Interview openings

1. Introduce interviewer and recap on project, interview aims and duration. Highlight the scope of this interview as regarding the EU level.
2. Double check on ethical procedures: Participant Information Sheet seen, Consent Form signed, including consent for audio recording interview.

Indicative questions and discussion prompts to aid interview discussion

1. Introductory and participant background questions
 - Please tell me about your current role and main work areas?
 - Please tell me about your professional background (e.g. past roles and academic disciplinary background)?
2. Describing current use of policy evaluation
 - Please tell me about your current approaches to policy evaluation? Are there standard approaches that you must use (e.g. UK Government 'Green Book', cost-benefit analysis, EC Impact Assessment guidelines)?
 - What are the criteria or standards that constitute a "good" outcome according to these current approaches to evaluation?
 - Does your appraisal process consider uncertainty, diversity of actors, long time horizons, innovation or radical transformation of markets? (move through these slowly, one at a time)
3. Describing current use of models
 - What does the term 'model' mean to you?
 - Which of your current work areas involve using models?
 - Which of your current work areas involve using the outputs from models (e.g. data and scenarios)?
 - Which specific models (or, outputs of which models) do you use and how do you access these models or outputs?
 - Have you used others in the past?
 - At which point(s) in the policy process do you use these models or outputs; what is the purpose or intention of their use?
 - How and to what extent do you use models to predict policy outcomes? How and to what extent do you use models to appraise impacts of existing policies?
4. Exploring the choice of models (If multiple models are used, repeat these questions for each model)
 - Why do you use this model; how did you come to choose it?
 - To what extent was this an expected or standard choice; to what extent have you considered other options?
 - What do you see as the strengths or advantages of this choice?
 - What do you see as the limitations or disadvantages of this choice?
 - (If they have considered other options: What are the most important differences between the options?)
 - As far as you know, what are the main assumptions of this model; what does it include and exclude, what type of data is used as input?
5. Experiences of using models in practice
 - Can you tell me about any times when model outputs have had tangible impacts on policy (for example, specific documents drawing on model outputs)?

- Have there been instances when models/outputs have not been used so effectively; or have not had the desired effect on policy – if so, can you describe what happened and why? (This includes models having less effect than expected, but also having any negative effects)
 - Other than direct policy influence, can you tell me about any ways that models and their outputs have informed your work?
 - Have there been instances when you have had to alter or adapt the way you use models or their outputs; if so, what happened and why?
 - Thinking back to the limitations or disadvantages you mentioned earlier, how do these affect the way that you use the model/outputs? (Are there certain ways in which you would not use it?)
6. Communities and cultures around models
- To what extent do you engage with modellers and discuss your needs and priorities with them?
 - To what extent do modellers understand and meet your needs; have you encountered any challenges when engaging with them? Are there clear gaps where your needs are not met (areas where models might be useful)?
 - To what extent are your understandings of models shared with your colleagues internally, and policyworker contacts externally? (e.g. Are there any tensions around the use of different models, or differing interpretations of outputs?).
7. Alternative and wider perspectives
- In what ways could the models you use, or the way they are applied, be improved?
 - To what extent have you considered using approaches other than modelling to achieve the goals we have been discussing? (refer back to answer under theme 2, if helpful)
 - What other kinds of data and methods are (or might be) useful in complementing the models you use?

Interview closings

1. Ask if there is anything further the interviewee wishes to add.
2. Thank the interviewee for their time.
3. Explain next steps and outputs of the project.